

Short report

Connectivity in transfusion medicine: Challenges, benefits, and goals

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ABSTRACT

Transfusion medicine requires meticulous record keeping from the time a blood donation is made to the time a patient receives a transfusion. As such, blood collection establishments and processing laboratories generate large amounts of data. This data must be managed, analyzed, and visualized appropriately to ensure safety of the blood supply. Today, the use of information technology (IT) solutions for data management in transfusion medicine varies widely between institutions. In this report, blood center professionals describe how they currently use IT solutions to improve their blood processing methods, the challenges they have, and how they envision IT solutions improving transfusion medicine in the future.

1. Introduction

On January 26, 2023, representatives from five different blood establishments and the medical device industry met to discuss the current and future role of information technology (IT) in medical device connectivity, data management, and data analysis to improve transfusion medicine processes. While each establishment was at different stages of their journey to enhanced (i.e., smart) IT connectivity, participants described similar challenges, gains, and future goals for IT solutions in blood banking and transfusion medicine.

2. Methods

Representatives from blood establishments were invited to participate in the meeting based on their expressed interest in IT connectivity. All levels of experience with connectivity were included, with participant experience ranging from pre-implementation of software solutions to nearly a decade of experience with software solutions. Participation occurred in a roundtable format, in which each representative contributed their knowledge and opinions on IT connectivity, followed by time for other participants to respond.

3. Results

3.1. The value of IT and data management solutions in transfusion medicine

At each blood center, the initial value of IT connectivity was realized in its potential to improve efficiency and increase traceability. Manual processes and record keeping come with the risk of human error. These errors may result in discarded products and time spent performing investigations and/or evaluations to ensure that they don't happen again. Moreover, audits by regulatory agencies increasingly request data tracing and operation logging. Representatives from each blood center concluded that investing in IT and data management solutions already has increased or would increase their center's efficiency, especially in transfusion services with multiple collection sites spread over large geographic areas. The ability to review records and program procedural changes remotely was considered highly beneficial by all participants, including those who have just started their journey towards smarter IT solutions.

Those who had already started software interconnectivity with collection, processing, or laboratory devices in their centers emphasized that the ability to program step-by-step SOP adherence measures with

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their devices has decreased discard rates and improved operator confidence. SOP adherence through IT applications guides operators to make the correct procedural choices (e.g., which PRT sets to use, what volume of PAS to add, etc.). This benefit was recognized by blood center leadership even though quantitative studies comparing periods before and after software implementation have yet to be completed.

Participants noted that along with increased efficiency, improved traceability was a key factor in their decision to implement IT solutions. Current IT solutions can create detailed reports for processes and for each blood product that meet or exceed regulatory requirements. The possibility to collect and merge all data from the establishment BBIS (blood bank information system) and devices makes integral validation of systems possible on a daily basis, which allows for real-time monitoring and informed process improvements. Moreover, the ability to access procedural data remotely at the click of a button also simplifies troubleshooting, as technicians may not have to travel from site to site to review data and update devices, adding a positive carbon footprint aspect to the mix.

3.2. Challenges with IT solutions

While some of the challenges blood centers face with manual data capture and operator training can be alleviated by the implementation of software programs, participants noted that several challenges remain. For example, blood collection sites must have up-to-date IT infrastructure, such as servers and internet connections, that can support electronic data capture and bidirectional communication between devices and information management systems. Existing IT infrastructure may sometimes require major upgrades, which can be costly and time intensive, especially in the aftermath of global network equipment shortages exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic [1].

Another challenge participants noted was in determining what data is the most useful to analyze. With improved IT connectivity, seemingly endless amounts of data can be generated from each device, procedure, and operator; however, without the proper analysis, the data means nothing. One representative noted that “[they] collect a lot of data, but don’t use most of it because it’s difficult to analyze.” Some centers already utilize software programs like the Trima Accel® Key Performance Indicator (KPI) Dashboard and QLIK® to visualize performance data, but others would like a more comprehensive platform that can integrate and analyze data from multiple manufacturers’ devices – from blood collections to blood processing – into a customizable report. From a software development perspective, creating such reports is possible but difficult because each blood center has unique data analysis needs. For example, some centers may be most interested in benchmarking between collection sites, while others may be most interested in analyzing donor demographics. All participants agreed that optimal use of data will require knowledge of basic data science principles, therefore it may be beneficial to have dedicated data scientists on staff. The need for data science in healthcare has been acknowledged for many years yet remains a challenge [2–4].

3.3. Benefits of IT solutions

In addition to the improvements in efficiency and traceability, participants noted that the blood donor experience may also improve with better IT solutions. Because software can be configured to guide operators through processes in a step-by-step manner, they can more easily adhere to SOPs without having to recall the steps by memory or record information manually. Ideally, this allows the operator to expend more energy interacting with the donor and ensuring a comfortable donor experience. Additionally, software can be used to record donor hemovigilance information, such as vasovagal reactions and hematomas. Analysis of this data can signal areas where attention is needed and can provide opportunities for targeted staff training [5].

It was also noted that analyzing procedural data can help blood

centers maximize each donation. Several centers are already using data visualization tools to identify platelet donors who are eligible to donate doubles but currently only donate singles [5,6]. Seeing these data can allow for opportunities to collect more with each donation – a goal shared by all blood collection services. Furthermore, using IT solutions to provide a day-by-day visualization of performance may allow for continuous process improvements. This could be used, for example, to increase/decrease staff as needed and allow operators to diversify their activities within the blood establishment.

3.4. Goals and future vision for IT solutions

With advances in technology and increased use of artificial intelligence (AI), accurate forecasting of blood demands is now a possibility. Several blood centers and transfusion medicine services have detailed their experiences with AI to show that it can be useful in predicting blood donor behavior and blood component quality, among other things; however, routine use of AI has yet to be implemented [3,7,8]. In the latter half of the discussion, participants shared a future vision of transfusion medicine in which blood centers and hospitals can share information instantly to collect “the right product, at the right time, for the right patient.” Compliance to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) sets some restriction to the sharing information between blood collectors and hospitals; thus, an IT solution that allows for secure data sharing to overcome this issue is essential. In addition to the GDPR, regulatory agencies including the European Directorate for the Quality of Medicines and Healthcare (EDQM) and U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) have updated their requirements for data security to ensure patient/donor privacy, proper de-identification, and authorized use [9,10].

While at this time, blood collection services must collect blood “just in case” it’s needed by hospitals for transfusion, increased use of data management systems may help develop an algorithm that can be used to better predict blood supply and demand. Other future applications brought forth included the possibility to compare – under confidentiality and consent – efficiencies of different establishments, and real-time connectivity for the purposes of following-up a specific collection (e.g., HLA-matched collections) and vendor supply inventory management.

4. Conclusion

Despite the fact that representatives from blood collection establishments were at different points in their journey to smart connectivity, all participants agreed on current and future benefits of IT for blood center efficiency and safety. The goal of IT connectivity is to ensure the right blood products are available at the right time to meet patient needs, thus avoiding waste through expiration, redundancy, and non-adherence to SOPs.

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